

Data Analysis - Students' Behavioral Patterns in Integrated Writing Tasks: A Sequence Analysis Approach

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0 - Libraries

```
library(tidyverse) # Data manipulation
library(ggplot2) # Data visualization
library(knitr) # Table formatting
library(TAM) # MFRM
library(TraMineR) # Sequence analysis
library(WeightedCluster) # Clustering
library(lmerTest) # Linear mixed-effects model
library(emmeans) # Estimated marginal means (post-hoc comparisons)
library(vcd) # Visualizing categorical data
library(summarytools) # Summary statistics and descriptive tables
```

1 - Data Import

Sequence Dataset

The process of cleaning and preparing log data into sequences was conducted separately. Due to data sharing restrictions, the dataset is not included with this R code.

Below is an overview of the data structure.

	studID	task	task_type	task_order	1	2	3
3	0023	arg_nasc	argument	0	ST & highlight	ST & highlight	ST & highlight
4	0023	sum_nasc	summary	1	pause	pause	ST & highlight

Variable Descriptions

- *scriptID*: Unique identifiers for students' written outcomes.
- *studID*: Unique identifiers for students.
- *task*: Task prompt categorized into four groups: **sum_sosc**, **sum_nasc**, **arg_sosc**, and **arg_nasc**.
- *task_type*: Task type categories: **summary** and **argument**.
- *task_order*: Indicates task order: 0 = first task, 1 = second task.
- 1 to 61: Each column contains the corresponding state for one-minute timeframe.

Ratings Dataset

Dataset including the raw ratings given by raters to each written outcome.

Below is an overview of the data structure.

scriptID	task	raterID	criterion	rating
T01Neth-0023	sum_nasc	r01	mining	2
T01Neth-0023	sum_nasc	r01	precision	3
T01Neth-0023	sum_nasc	r01	processing	2

2 - MFRM: Text Quality

MFRM model for obtaining text quality scores of a each written product, while correcting for relative severity (`raterID`), task prompt difficulty (`task`), criteria difficulty (`criterion`), and criteria level (`step`).

```
formula <- ~ raterID + task + criterion + step

mfrm <- tam.mml.mfr(
  resp = ratings.long$rating,
  facets = select(ratings.long, task:criterion),
  pid = ratings.long$scriptID,
  formulaA = formula
)
```

```
text_quality <- tam.wle(mfrm)
```

```
Iteration in WLE/MLE estimation 1 | Maximal change 1.7009
Iteration in WLE/MLE estimation 2 | Maximal change 0.4171
Iteration in WLE/MLE estimation 3 | Maximal change 0.0214
Iteration in WLE/MLE estimation 4 | Maximal change 0.0003
Iteration in WLE/MLE estimation 5 | Maximal change 0
----
WLE Reliability= 0.785
```

Add obtained text quality scores to sequence data with patterns:

```
colnames(text_quality)[1] <- "scriptID"
kable(text_quality[1, 1:5])
```

scriptID	N.items	PersonScores	PersonMax	theta
T01Neth-0023	7	14	35	-0.6078526

```
data <- merge(data,
  text_quality[,c("scriptID", "theta")],
  by = "scriptID")
```

Model parameters

```
parameters <- as.data.frame(mfrm$xsi.facets)
kable(parameters[1:24, ])
```

parameter	facet	xsi	se.xsi
step1	step	-4.2563038	0.1208794
step2	step	-1.4579042	0.0319268
step3	step	-0.0396694	0.0220021
step4	step	1.6555514	0.0265282

parameter	facet	xsi	se.xsi
step5	step	2.6516942	0.0510757
raterIDr01	raterID	0.0550606	0.0201204
raterIDr02	raterID	-0.1039184	0.0200226
raterIDr03	raterID	0.0404491	0.0201103
raterIDr04	raterID	-0.0102795	0.0200907
raterIDr05	raterID	-0.0507386	0.0200538
raterIDr06	raterID	0.0694269	0.0448993
taskarg_nasc	task	-0.3589266	0.0164530
taskarg_sosc	task	0.1002455	0.0162538
tasksum_nasc	task	0.3915052	0.0177930
tasksum_sosc	task	-0.1328242	0.0291801
criterion_attribution	criterion	1.7853415	0.0277233
criterion_cohesion____	criterion	0.0519329	0.0233153
criterion_grammar_____	criterion	-0.2323633	0.0232000
criterion_mining_____	criterion	-0.4668797	0.0231234
criterion_precision____	criterion	-0.9919351	0.0230403
criterion_processing____	criterion	-0.7980500	0.0230528
criterion_structure____	criterion	0.4347724	0.0235095
criterion_synthesis____	criterion	-0.0057021	0.0267430
criterion_vocabulary____	criterion	0.2228834	0.0686680

3 - Sequence Analysis

Define sequence state labels and codes:

```
# List containing distinct states found in the data
seqstat1(data[,6:66])
```

```
[1] "burst"           "dictionary"      "editing"         "notes"
[5] "pause"          "source text"    "ST & highlight"
```

```
# Define the variables to create the state sequence object
state_order <- c("source text", "ST & highlight",
                "notes", "dictionary", "burst",
                "editing", "pause")
state_labels <- c("source text", "ST & highlighting",
                 "note-taking", "using dictionary", "writing fluently",
                 "writing editing", "pausing")
state_codes <- c("ST", "SH", "N", "D", "WF", "WE", "P")
```

Create sequences:

```
seq <- seqdef(data, 6:66,
              alphabet = state_order,
              states = state_codes,
              labels = state_labels,
              xtstep = 5)
```

Compute Optimal Matching (OM) distances using substitution costs based on transition rates observed in the data:

```
dist_matrix <- seqdist(seq,
                      method = "OMstran",
                      indel = 2,
                      otto = 0.5,
                      sm = "TRATE")
```

4 - Clustering

Hierarchical clustering using Ward's method:

```
hc_ward <- agnes(dist_matrix, diss = TRUE, method = "ward")
```

Evaluate cluster quality:

```
cluster_quality <- as.clustrange(hc_ward,
                                diss = dist_matrix,
                                ncluster = 10)
kable(summary(cluster_quality, max.rank = 3))
```

	1. N groups	1. stat	2. N groups	2. stat	3. N groups	3. stat
PBC	4	0.5245872	3	0.4742027	6	0.4090694
HG	4	0.6314194	3	0.5639019	6	0.5490989
HGSD	4	0.6314182	3	0.5639009	6	0.5490978
ASW	2	0.1488792	4	0.1477213	3	0.1462402
ASWw	4	0.1537154	2	0.1516071	3	0.1506329
CH	2	47.3140924	3	33.4113350	4	26.0138192
R2	10	0.1914958	9	0.1820463	8	0.1740441
CHsq	2	86.5931797	3	65.3787802	4	52.6286090
R2sq	10	0.3219323	9	0.3090615	8	0.2954684
HC	4	0.1719348	3	0.2060895	6	0.2171648

Cluster Quality Plot

```
cluster_quality <- as.data.frame(scale(cluster_quality$stats)) |>
  gather(Indicator, factor_key = T)

cluster_quality$cluster <- rep(c(2:10), 10)

cluster_quality <- cluster_quality[cluster_quality$Indicator %in% c("ASW", "PBC",
                                                                    "HG", "HC"),]

ggplot(cluster_quality,
        aes(x = cluster, y = value, linetype = Indicator, color = Indicator)) +
  theme_bw() +
  ylab("Standardized Value") +
  xlab("Number of Clusters") +
  geom_line(linewidth = 1) +
```

```
scale_linetype_manual(values = c("dotted", "longdash", "twodash","solid")) +
scale_color_manual(values = c("#000000", "#555555", "#999999", "#BBBBBB")) +
geom_vline(xintercept = 4, linetype = "dashed", linewidth = 0.5)
```


Cluster Membership and Visualization

Cluster membership from 4-cluster solution:

```
# Assign clusters
cl_4 <- cutree(hc_ward, k = 4)
cl_4_fac <- factor(cl_4, labels = paste("Type", 1:4))

# Add cluster variable to dataset
data$pattern <- cl_4_fac
```

State distribution plots for each cluster type:

```
# Define color palette
cpal(seq) <- c("#009E73", "#56B4E9", "#F0E442", "#0072B2",
              "#F0027F", "#CC79A7", "#3e4444")

# Plot state distributions for each cluster
seqdplot(seq,
          group = cl_4_fac,
          border = NA,
          xtstep = 5,
          xlab = "Time on Task (mins)")
```


5 - Relationship between Clusters (patterns) with Text Quality

Linear Mixed-Effects Model

```
# Fit the linear mixed-effects model
model <- lmer(theta ~ pattern*task_type + task_order + (1 | studID),
              data = data)

# Summary of the model
summary(model)
```

Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [lmerModLmerTest]
 Formula: theta ~ pattern * task_type + task_order + (1 | studID)
 Data: data

REML criterion at convergence: 1551

Scaled residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-3.06969	-0.46183	0.00138	0.46523	2.49007

Random effects:

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
studID	(Intercept)	0.4137	0.6432
	Residual	0.4560	0.6753

Number of obs: 590, groups: studID, 374

Fixed effects:

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value
(Intercept)	0.0455337	0.0753281	579.6158377	0.604
patternType 2	-0.2390883	0.1337375	559.6064329	-1.788
patternType 3	0.1807595	0.1698376	561.5190225	1.064
patternType 4	0.3341350	0.1332294	540.9253819	2.508
task_typesummary	-0.0636701	0.0912392	414.3137689	-0.698
task_order	0.0004074	0.0627020	263.2335545	0.006
patternType 2:task_typesummary	0.1892702	0.1804339	499.8733868	1.049
patternType 3:task_typesummary	-0.2495122	0.2513913	449.6208775	-0.993
patternType 4:task_typesummary	0.1298288	0.2038548	379.8767799	0.637

Pr(>|t|)

(Intercept)	0.5458
patternType 2	0.0744 .
patternType 3	0.2876
patternType 4	0.0124 *
task_typesummary	0.4857
task_order	0.9948
patternType 2:task_typesummary	0.2947
patternType 3:task_typesummary	0.3215
patternType 4:task_typesummary	0.5246

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Correlation of Fixed Effects:

	(Intr)	pttrT2	pttrT3	pttrT4	tsk_ty	tsk_rd	ptT2:_	ptT3:_
patternTyp2	-0.474							
patternTyp3	-0.378	0.190						
patternTyp4	-0.489	0.254	0.230					
tsk_typsmmr	-0.563	0.320	0.247	0.337				
task_order	-0.379	0.100	0.081	0.098	0.032			
pttrnT2:ts_	0.274	-0.679	-0.111	-0.147	-0.520	0.023		
pttrnT3:ts_	0.231	-0.122	-0.619	-0.120	-0.389	-0.013	0.189	
pttrnT4:ts_	0.259	-0.157	-0.124	-0.557	-0.462	0.039	0.236	0.174

Pairwise comparisons among patterns (post-hoc)

```
# Compute pairwise contrasts
pair_contrast <- emmeans(model, list(pairwise ~ pattern), adjust = "tukey")

pair_contrast
```

```
$`emmeans of pattern`
  pattern  emmean      SE  df lower.CL upper.CL
Type 1    0.0139 0.0564 482  -0.0969  0.1247
Type 2   -0.1306 0.0873 567  -0.3020  0.0409
Type 3    0.0699 0.1280 575  -0.1808  0.3206
Type 4    0.4130 0.1060 579   0.2043  0.6216
```

Results are averaged over the levels of: task_type, task_order
Degrees-of-freedom method: kenward-roger
Confidence level used: 0.95

```
$`pairwise differences of pattern`
  1          estimate      SE  df t.ratio p.value
Type 1 - Type 2    0.144 0.0986 581   1.465  0.4591
Type 1 - Type 3   -0.056 0.1350 561  -0.414  0.9761
Type 1 - Type 4   -0.399 0.1140 555  -3.487  0.0030
Type 2 - Type 3   -0.200 0.1500 570  -1.334  0.5417
Type 2 - Type 4   -0.544 0.1310 567  -4.143  0.0002
Type 3 - Type 4   -0.343 0.1580 523  -2.178  0.1308
```

Results are averaged over the levels of: task_type, task_order
Degrees-of-freedom method: kenward-roger
P value adjustment: tukey method for comparing a family of 4 estimates

Visualizing Text Quality by Pattern

```
plot <- as.data.frame(pair_contrast$`emmeans of pattern`)

plot$pattern <- factor(plot$pattern,
                      levels = c("Type 4", "Type 3", "Type 2", "Type 1"),
                      labels = c("Type 4 (strategic)",
                                  "Type 3 (note-taking)",
                                  "Type 2 (low-interaction)",
                                  "Type 1 (rapid)"))

ggplot(plot, aes(x = pattern, y = emmean)) +
  geom_point(size = 3) +
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin = lower.CL, ymax = upper.CL), width = 0.2) +
  labs(x = "Pattern", y = "Text Quality") +
  theme_minimal() +
  coord_flip()
```


6 - Patterns Consistency

Transform data into wide format and filter participants who completed two integrated tasks ($n = 216$):

```
data_wide <- data[,c("studID", "task_type", "pattern", "task_order")] %>%
  pivot_wider(names_from = c(task_order), values_from = c(pattern, task_type))

# Keep participants with two tasks
data_wide <- data_wide[complete.cases(data_wide),]
```

Table of frequencies

Pattern of first task = pattern_0

Pattern of second task = pattern_1

```
ctable(data_wide$pattern_1,
       data_wide$pattern_0,
       prop = "c",
       headings = FALSE)
```

pattern_1	pattern_0	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type 4	Total
Type 1		91 (85.8%)	20 (41.7%)	9 (40.9%)	20 (50.0%)	140 (64.8%)
Type 2		8 (7.5%)	21 (43.8%)	2 (9.1%)	2 (5.0%)	33 (15.3%)
Type 3		4 (3.8%)	1 (2.1%)	7 (31.8%)	5 (12.5%)	17 (7.9%)
Type 4		3 (2.8%)	6 (12.5%)	4 (18.2%)	13 (32.5%)	26 (12.0%)
Total		106 (100.0%)	48 (100.0%)	22 (100.0%)	40 (100.0%)	216 (100.0%)

Cramer's V

```
assocstats(table(data_wide$pattern_0,  
                 data_wide$pattern_1))
```

	X ²	df	P(> X ²)
Likelihood Ratio	77.711	9	0.0000000000004598544
Pearson	90.933	9	0.000000000000011102

Phi-Coefficient : NA
Contingency Coeff.: 0.544
Cramer's V : 0.375

Subset of different task types

Subset of participants, whose task combination included two integrated tasks of different types: one summary and one argumentative task.

```
diff_type <- data_wide[which(data_wide$task_type_0 != data_wide$task_type_1),]  
assocstats(table(diff_type$pattern_0, diff_type$pattern_1))
```

	X ²	df	P(> X ²)
Likelihood Ratio	40.130	9	0.00000719809
Pearson	45.958	9	0.00000061313

Phi-Coefficient : NA
Contingency Coeff.: 0.498
Cramer's V : 0.332

Subset of same task types

Subset of participants, whose task combination included two integrated tasks of the same type: either two summaries or two argumentative tasks.

```
same_type <- data_wide[which(data_wide$task_type_1 == data_wide$task_type_0),]  
assocstats(table(same_type$pattern_1, same_type$pattern_0))
```

	X ²	df	P(> X ²)
Likelihood Ratio	43.923	9	0.0000014585
Pearson	49.827	9	0.0000001161

Phi-Coefficient : NA
Contingency Coeff.: 0.627
Cramer's V : 0.464

Session Information

```
sessionInfo()
```

```
R version 4.4.2 (2024-10-31 ucrt)
Platform: x86_64-w64-mingw32/x64
Running under: Windows 10 x64 (build 19045)
```

```
Matrix products: default
```

```
locale:
```

```
[1] LC_COLLATE=German_Germany.utf8 LC_CTYPE=German_Germany.utf8
[3] LC_MONETARY=German_Germany.utf8 LC_NUMERIC=C
[5] LC_TIME=German_Germany.utf8
```

```
time zone: Europe/Berlin
```

```
tzcode source: internal
```

```
attached base packages:
```

```
[1] grid      stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets  methods
[8] base
```

```
other attached packages:
```

```
[1] summarytools_1.0.1    vcd_1.4-13            emmeans_1.10.5
[4] lmerTest_3.1-3        lme4_1.1-35.5        Matrix_1.7-1
[7] WeightedCluster_1.8-0 cluster_2.1.6         TraMineR_2.2-10
[10] TAM_4.2-21           CDM_8.2-6            mvtnorm_1.3-1
[13] knitr_1.48           lubridate_1.9.3      forcats_1.0.0
[16] stringr_1.5.1        dplyr_1.1.4          purrr_1.0.2
[19] readr_2.1.5          tidyr_1.3.1          tibble_3.2.1
[22] ggplot2_3.5.1        tidyverse_2.0.0
```

```
loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
```

```
[1] tcltk_4.4.2          permute_0.9-7         sandwich_3.1-1
[4] rlang_1.1.4          magrittr_2.0.3       multcomp_1.4-26
[7] matrixStats_1.4.1   compiler_4.4.2       mgcv_1.9-1
[10] vctrs_0.6.5         reshape2_1.4.4       pkgconfig_2.0.3
[13] fastmap_1.2.0       backports_1.5.0      magick_2.8.5
[16] labeling_0.4.3      pander_0.6.5         utf8_1.2.4
[19] rmarkdown_2.29      tzdb_0.4.0           nloptr_2.1.1
[22] xfun_0.51           jsonlite_1.8.8       pryr_0.1.6
[25] broom_1.0.6         parallel_4.4.2       R6_2.5.1
[28] vegclust_2.0.2      stringi_1.8.4        RColorBrewer_1.1-3
[31] parallelly_1.38.0   boot_1.3-31          lmtest_0.9-40
[34] numDeriv_2016.8-1.1 estimability_1.5.1   Rcpp_1.0.13
[37] iterators_1.0.14    future.apply_1.11.3  zoo_1.8-12
[40] base64enc_0.1-3     polycor_0.8-1        splines_4.4.2
[43] nnet_7.3-19         timechange_0.3.0     tidyselect_1.2.1
[46] rstudioapi_0.16.0  yaml_2.3.10          vegan_2.6-8
[49] codetools_0.2-20    admisc_0.36          listenv_0.9.1
[52] lattice_0.22-6      plyr_1.8.9           withr_3.0.1
```

[55]	coda_0.19-4.1	evaluate_1.0.0	future_1.34.0
[58]	survival_3.7-0	pillar_1.9.0	checkmate_2.3.2
[61]	foreach_1.5.2	generics_0.1.3	hms_1.1.3
[64]	munsell_0.5.1	scales_1.3.0	minqa_1.2.8
[67]	globals_0.16.3	xtable_1.8-4	glue_1.7.0
[70]	tools_4.4.2	fastcluster_1.2.6	rappor-tools_1.1
[73]	colorspace_2.1-1	nlme_3.1-166	cli_3.6.3
[76]	fansi_1.0.6	doFuture_1.0.1	gtable_0.3.5
[79]	digest_0.6.37	progressr_0.15.0	pbkrtest_0.5.3
[82]	TH.data_1.1-2	farver_2.1.2	htmltools_0.5.8.1
[85]	lifecycle_1.0.4	MASS_7.3-61	